

Optimization of prokaryotic DNA isolation in the precious red coral *Corallium rubrum* for metagenomic analyses

Gervais Ophélie^{1,2}, Christine Ferrier-Pagès², Romie Tignat-Perrier^{1,2}

¹ Unité de Recherche sur la Biologie des Coraux Précieux CSM - CHANEL, Centre Scientifique de Monaco, 8 Quai Antoine 1^{er}, MC 98000, Principality of Monaco

² Coral Biology Team, Centre Scientifique de Monaco, 8 Quai Antoine 1^{er}, MC 98000, Principality of Monaco

Summary

The diversity of the bacterial communities associated with *Corallium rubrum* is increasingly well characterized (Van de Water et al. 2016; 2024; Prioux et al. 2023). Notably, *C. rubrum* microbiome is dominated by bacteria affiliated with the phylum *Spirochaetota* and exhibits a remarkable stability across both space and time (van de Water et al., 2016; 2018). Despite these taxonomic insights, the functional roles of these microorganisms within the holobiont remain largely unknown. To address this gap, we seek to 1) reconstruct metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) of the dominant taxa and 2) investigate their functional roles in *C. rubrum*.

A key difficulty in conducting metagenomic analyses on holobionts, compared to free-living microbes, is the predominance of host-derived DNA in the samples. After sequencing total genomic DNA, most of the reads are usually derived from the host genome (often more than 98%), with only a small proportion corresponding to microbial sequences. Moreover, the selective isolation of microbial DNA from a mixed pool of host and microbial DNA is technically demanding, often requiring specialized depletion or capture methods that are difficult to optimize.

To overcome these challenges, we developed a pre-extraction protocol, designed to enrich samples for microbial DNA, by separating host cells from the associated microorganisms. Adapted and optimized from Bruggeling et al. (2021), our protocol consists into two phases: 1) cellular dissociation: microbial cells, host cells and sclerites (small calcareous structures embedded in the red coral tissue) are dissociated using a combination of enzymatic (collagenase

IV or proteinase K) and mechanical digestion (mortar or ULTRA-TURRAX homogenizer) on tissue samples; 2) differential lysis: host cells are selectively lysed using the detergent Triton X-100, and the released host DNA is then degraded with DNase. Because bacterial cells remain intact during this step, they can subsequently be isolated and processed using a standard microbial DNA extraction protocol. qPCR analyses and metagenomic sequencing validated the efficacy of this approach, showing a significant enrichment of the microbial fraction: while standard extractions typically yield <2% of non-host sequences, our method achieved 30 to 58% of non-host sequences. This 15-to-30-fold increase in microbial signal significantly enhances the feasibility and cost effectiveness of MAG reconstruction from marine holobionts.

Materials and Methods

Coral collection

Several coral samples (\approx 4 cm long) maintained in the aquarium facility of the Centre Scientifique de Monaco, in the dark and at 15°C, were used in this experiment. Coral tissue was removed from the skeleton using a sterile scalpel and transferred in a 5 mL tube filled with 4 mL of magnesium/calcium-free seawater (Mg/Ca-free SW).

Bacterial DNA isolation

Several treatments were compared to evaluate their effectiveness for bacterial DNA isolation. Untreated control samples were compared with samples subjected to the following pre-treatments:

*Differential enzymatic digestion: tissue samples were treated with 20 μ L of either collagenase IV (1X final concentration) or Proteinase K (600 U/mL) during 2 h at 60°C, followed by 15 min at 70°C.

*Differential physical digestion: mechanical tissue dissociation was performed using either a mortar and pestle or an ULTRA-TURRAX homogenizer.

*Tissue homogenate filtration: For all treatments, tissue homogenate was then filtered through both 30 μ m and 10 μ m filters (pluriStrainer cell strainer, PluriSelect) to filter debris, sclerites and big (host) cells. The filtrate was centrifuged at 10'000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C. The supernatant was removed.

*Host lysis with a DNase treatment: the cell-enriched pellet was resuspended either in Triton/Turbo DNase mix or only Triton, and incubated at 37°C for 30 min. Triton/Turbo DNase mix was used to selectively lyse coral cells and digest free host DNA. One mL of PBS was added and prior to centrifugation at 10'000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C. The supernatant was removed.

*All samples (either control or pre-treated) were subjected to a classic microbial DNA extraction using the DNeasy PowerBiofilm Kit (Qiagen) including a bead beating step. The concentration of DNA was quantified using the Qubit™ dsDNA BR assay on the Qubit™ 3 fluorometer (Invitrogen).

Quantitative PCR protocol

qPCRs essays were performed to evaluate differences in the abundance of coral DNA (based on the abundance of the host *beta-actin* gene) and total bacterial DNA or *Spirochaetaceae* DNA (based on the abundance of the *16S rRNA* gene). Each reaction was performed in duplicate on a QuantStudio3 qPCR machine (Applied Biosystems). Amplification reactions contained 0.4 µL of each primer at concentrations reported in Table 1, 10 µL of SYBR Green master mix and 2 µL of DNA in a final volume of 20 µL. The amplification program was carried out using standard cycling conditions: 95°C for 10 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95°C for 15 s and 60°C for 1 min.

For relative quantification of bacterial enrichment, data were analysed using the method described by Pfaffl (2001), and two complementary approaches were used. First, a normalized fold-change method was applied to evaluate bacterial DNA abundance relative to host beta-actin (CrDNA) and control samples were used for calibration. Second, to directly assess the effect of the DNase treatment on each specific target (including the host DNA itself), a direct ratio ($2^{-\Delta Ct}$) was calculated between DNase-treated (DNase+) and untreated (DNase-) samples without normalization.

Gene	Sequences 5'-3'	Primer concentration (µM)	Amplicon length (bp)	Efficacies (%)	Reference
Bacterial 16S rRNA gene	Forward ACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAG	4	200	101,78	Fierer et al. 2005
	Reverse ATTACCGCGGCTGCTGG				
Spirochaetaceae 16S rRNA gene	Forward YCCTGGGCTACACACGT	3,1	140	96,6	Husmann et al. 2010
	Reverse GTTACGACTTCACCCTCCT				
Corallium rubrum's beta-actin gene	Forward GCCAGCAGTTCAAGTTTGGA	3	129	101,78	Unpublished data
	Reverse ACCAGCAGATTCCATCCCA				

Table 1: Sequences and amplification efficiencies of the different qPCR primer pairs used for each targeted gene.

Statistical analyses

Statistical differences in DNA concentration, total bacterial DNA abundance, and *Spirochaetaceae* DNA abundance across the different treatments were evaluated using Student's t-tests. Kruskal-Wallis tests followed by Dunn's post-hoc tests were performed to compare samples treated with or without DNase. All statistical tests were performed using R v4.3.1 and rstatix v.0.7.3.

Library preparation and sequencing

Four samples were prepared using the selected protocol provided in Appendix 1 and sent to Prebiomics (Trento, Italy). Libraries were prepared and sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000Dx as 150 bp paired-end reads yielding an average of 25M reads per sample.

Preprocessing

Bioinformatic analyses were performed on CentOS Linux server 7.9. Quality of the reads was first checked using fastQC v.0.11.9 (Andrews, 2023) and multiQC v.1.13 (Ewels et al., 2016). Sequencing barcodes and adapters were removed using Trimmomatic v.0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014) and reads were trimmed once the average quality in a 4 bp window fell below 15, cut bases off the extremities if below a quality score of 20. Short reads (<36 bp) were removed. Reads corresponding to the host *C. rubrum* but also the mussel *Mytilus edulis* and the shrimp *Artemia franciscana* on which corals fed throughout the experiments, were removed using bwa-mem2 v.2.2.1 (Vasimuddin et al., 2019) and reference genomes ((Ganot et al., 2024), GCA_025215535.1 and GCA_019857095.1).

Results

Several approaches were evaluated to optimize host tissue digestion prior to establishing the final protocol. Tissue dissociation using either a pestle and mortar or a ULTRA-TURRAX homogenizer showed no significant difference (Figure1A); therefore the ULTRA-TURRAX was selected for its greater ease of use. In contrast, the comparison of enzymatic treatments (Collagenase IV versus Proteinase K) revealed differences in bacterial signal (Figure1B). The use

of Proteinase K instead of Collagenase IV significantly increased the total bacterial signal (p-value = 0.04) and the *Spirochaetaceae* signal (p-value = 0.031). Proteinase K was therefore retained in the final protocol.

Figure 1: Relative enrichment of bacterial DNA in differentially treated samples compared to untreated control samples. Fold change of bacterial 16S rRNA gene in samples treated with pestle and mortar or using an ULTRA-TURRAX, relative to untreated control corals (A). Relative expression of bacterial 16S rRNA (bactDNA) and *Spirochaetaceae* 16S rRNA (spiroDNA) gene in sample treated with collagenase IV or Proteinase K, relative to untreated control corals. Relative expression were calculated using the Pfaffl method.

The figures below compare samples following the complete upstream validated protocol, with (DNase+) or without (DNase-) subsequent DNase treatment, against non-enriched controls.

DNase treatment (DNase+) following host cell lysis using Triton led to a significant reduction (4-fold lower) of total DNA concentration in the supernatant compared to untreated samples (DNase-) (p-value < 0.001, Figure 2). This decrease in total DNA was likely associated with a

decrease in host DNA, as we observed an increase in the abundance of bacterial DNA (Figure 3). Indeed, bacterial and *Spirochaetaceae* DNA abundances increased up to 50 and 150 times, respectively, in DNase+ samples compared to control samples (Figure 3). Furthermore, these bacterial DNA levels were significantly higher in DNase+ samples than in DNase- samples (p-value = 0.04 for total bacteria and p-value = 0.03 for *Spirochaetaceae*; Figure 3). This was confirmed by a direct ΔC_t comparison ($2^{-\Delta C_t}$), showing a net signal amplification of > 10-fold for total bacteria and > 30-fold for *Spirochaetaceae* in DNase-treated samples, while host coral DNA (CrDNA) was depleted (value < 0, Figure 4). Altogether, these findings indicate that the complete workflow (including DNase treatment) successfully increases the ratio of bacterial to host DNA, thereby confirming bacterial enrichment.

Figure 2: Total DNA concentration in treated samples. Comparison of DNA concentration (ng/μl) between samples subjected to all treatments except DNase (DNase-) and those subjected to all treatments including DNase (DNase+) following host cell lysis.

Figure 3: Relative enrichment of bacterial DNA in differentially treated samples (DNase+ and DNase-) compared to untreated coral samples. Relative expression of bacterial *16S rRNA* (bactDNA) and *Spirochaetaceae* 16S rRNA (spiroDNA) gene in samples treated (DNase+) or not (DNase-) with DNase, relative to untreated control samples. Relative expression were calculated using the Pfaffl method.

Figure 4: Relative enrichment of coral and bacterial DNA in DNase-treated samples (DNase+) compared to non-DNase-treated samples (DNase-). Fold change comparison ($2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$) of bacterial *16S rRNA* (bactDNA), *Spirochaetaceae* 16S rRNA (spiroDNA) and red coral beta-actin gene

(CrDNA) between samples treated with or without DNase is plotted. Value greater than 1 indicate an enrichment in the DNase+ condition, while values less than 1 indicate a depletion.

Four samples were sent to sequencing to quantify the efficiency of the bacterial enrichment protocol compared to standard total DNA extractions. Prior to preprocessing, the median sequencing depth was equal to 2.54×10^8 reads. Trimming slightly reduced this median to 2.48×10^8 reads (Figure 5). The last step involved filtering sequences mapped to the host genome or it's known food sources. Following this step, a median number of 1.18×10^8 reads was retained. At the end of the preprocessing pipeline, between 30 and 58% of the total reads were retained, corresponding to microbial sequences. This represents a substantial improvement over standard non-enriched samples.

Figure 5: Read depth across different stages of bioinformatic preprocessing. Number of reads per sample at each step of the preprocessing analyses.

The final bacterial enrichment protocol is provided in the Appendix 1 and summarized in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Protocol for bacterial enrichment. Coral tissue contains host cells, microbial cells, but also sclerites. Therefore, coral tissue is enzymatically and physically digested using a combination of enzymatic and mechanical digestion. The supernatant is then filtered through 2 different filters of 30 and 10 μm . The cell suspension is then treated with 0.006% Triton X-100 to selectively lyse coral cells while maintaining bacterial cell integrity. Subsequent DNase treatment degrades the free host DNA. The remaining suspension then has a reduced coral DNA content, leaving intact bacterial cells who are then submitted to a classic microbial DNA extraction protocol.

Discussion

Extracting high-quality microbial metagenomic DNA from a coral holobiont such as *Corallium rubrum* presents significant technical hurdles, primarily due to the complex morphology of the holobiont. Unlike simpler marine organisms, *C. rubrum* possesses a dense, resilient collagenous matrix embedded with a high density of calcitic sclerites. This structural complexity often resists standard cellular dissociation, leading to poor microbial recovery. Furthermore, the

overwhelming dominance of host DNA typically suppresses the microbial signal during sequencing, often resulting in libraries where over 98% of the reads are host-derived.

To mitigate these limitations, we implemented and refined a pre-extraction enrichment protocol adapted from Bruggeling et al. (2021). The methodology was optimized to maximize the microbial-to-host DNA ratio through two stages. First, constituents (*i.e.*, host cells, microbial cells, and sclerites) of coral tissue was dissociated using an initial digestion with Proteinase K, supplemented by high-shear mechanical disruption (ULTRA-TURRAX homogenizer). Second, we employed a differential lysis strategy using a low-concentration (0.006%) Triton X-100 solution. This concentration was specifically calibrated to permeabilize the more fragile host cell membranes while leaving the structurally distinct bacterial cells intact. Subsequent treatment with DNase allowed for the selective degradation of the liberated host DNA prior to the final microbial DNA extraction, significantly enriching samples in microbial sequences. While standard extraction typically yields less than 2% of microbial sequences, this optimized protocol resulted in libraries containing 30 to 58% of microbial reads. This enrichment significantly enhances the resolution of de novo metagenomic assembly and allows for a more comprehensive recovery of low abundance functional genes that would otherwise remain undetected.

References

- Andrews, S., 2023. FastQC: a quality control tool for high throughput sequence data.
- Bolger, A.M., Lohse, M., Usadel, B., 2014. Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 30, 2114–2120. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btu170>
- Carlijn E. Bruggeling, Daniel R. Garza, Soumia Achouiti, Wouter Mes, Bas E. Dutilh, Annemarie Boleij. Optimized bacterial DNA isolation method for microbiome analysis of human tissues. *Microbiology Open*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mbo3.1191>
- Ewels, P., Magnusson, M., Lundin, S., Källér, M., 2016. MultiQC: summarize analysis results for multiple tools and samples in a single report. *Bioinformatics* 32, 3047–3048. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btw354>
- Ganot, P., Rausch, T., Fritz, M., Zoccola, D., Wang, X., Aranda, M., Benes, V., Allemand, D., Tambutté, S., 2024. Genome sequence of the Mediterranean red coral *Corallium rubrum*. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-4582739/v1>
- Pfaffl, M.W. (2001) A new mathematical model for relative quantification in real-time RT-PCR. *Nucleic Acids Res* 29: e45.
- Prioux, C., Tignat-Perrier, R., Gervais, O. *et al.* Unveiling microbiome changes in Mediterranean octocorals during the 2022 marine heatwaves: quantifying key bacterial symbionts and potential pathogens, 2023. *Microbiome* 11, 271. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40168-023-01711-x>

- Vasimuddin, Md., Misra, S., Li, H., Aluru, S., 2019. Efficient Architecture-Aware Acceleration of BWA-MEM for Multicore Systems. 2019 IEEE Int. Parallel Distrib. Process. Symp. IPDPS 314–324. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPS.2019.00041>
- van de Water, J.A.J.M., Melkonian, R., Junca, H., Voolstra, C.R., Reynaud, S., Allemand, D., Ferrier-Pagès, C., 2016. Spirochaetes dominate the microbial community associated with the red coral *Corallium rubrum* on a broad geographic scale. *Sci. Rep.* 6, 27277. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep27277>
- van de Water, J.A.J.M., Voolstra, C.R., Rottier, C., Cocito, S., Peirano, A., Allemand, D., Ferrier-Pagès, C., 2018. Seasonal Stability in the Microbiomes of Temperate Gorgonians and the Red Coral *Corallium rubrum* Across the Mediterranean Sea. *Microbial Ecology*. Vol. 75, No.1, 274-288. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00248-017-1006-y>
- van de Water, J.A.J.M., Allemand, D., Ferrier-Pagès, C., 2024. Bacterial symbionts of the precious coral *Corallium rubrum* are differentially distributed across colony-specific compartments and differ among colormorphs. *Environ. Microbiol. Rep.* 16, e13236. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1758-2229.13236>

Appendix 1: Protocol of bacterial DNA isolation

Material

- Scalpel
- Petri dish
- 2, 5 and 50 mL tubes
- Incubator
- ULTRA-TURRAX® (IKA) homogenizer
- pluriStrainer cell strainer 30 and 10 µm (PluriSelect)
- Mg/Ca-free SW
- PBS 1X
- 1% Triton X-100
- Proteinase K (600 U/mL)
- Turbo DNase (2U/µL, Ambion)
- DNAeasy PowerBiofilm Kit (Qiagen)

Before you start

- Prepare 0.006% Triton X-100: 60 µL 1% Triton X-100 + 9940 µL PBS 1X

Tissue collection

1. Cut a piece of coral (≈ 4 cm long) and remove the tissue from the skeleton using a sterile scalpel in a petri dish with 4 mL of Mg/Ca-free SW. Transfer the tissue and the Mg/Ca-free SW in a 5 mL tube.

Host tissue digestion

2. Add 20 μL of Proteinase K and incubate at 60°C for 2h with regular mix followed by 15 min at 70°C (to inactivate the Proteinase K)
3. Dissociate the tissue with an alcohol-purified ULTRA-TURRAX®
4. Filter the homogenate through a 30 μm filter into a 50 mL tube (to remove sclerite, debris and big cells), rinse the 5 mL tube with 1 mL of Mg/Ca-free SW and filter it in the same 50 mL tube.
5. Filter again with a 10 μm filter in a new 50 mL tube.
6. Distribute the filtrate into several 2 mL tubes (≈ 1.6 mL/tube) and centrifuge at 10000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C.
7. Remove the supernatant

Host cell lysis and DNA digestion

8. add 200 μL of Triton/Turbo DNase Mix:
 - 176 μL 0.006% Triton X-100
 - 20 μL of 10X Turbo DNase buffer
 - 4 μL of Turbo DNase
9. Resuspend the pellet by vortexing
10. Spin down the sample and incubate at 37°C for 30min.
11. Group the entire sample in a 2 mL tube and add 1mL PBS.
12. Centrifuge at 10000 rpm for 15 min at 4°C.
13. Remove the supernatant and freeze at -20°C (or -80°C) or extract DNA directly using the DNAeasy PowerBiofilm Kit and Bead Beating